

2024 - Summary of the Conformity of IPBES products to the DKMP - Status, Lessons Learned and Recommendations

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Version 2.0

Date: 3 June 2024

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.11613859](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11613859)

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Introduction

This report assesses the compliance of three key IPBES assessments - the Sustainable Use Assessment (SUA), the Values Assessment (VA) and the Invasive Alien Species Assessment (IAS) - with the IPBES Data and Knowledge Management Policy (DKMP). This policy ensures that all data and knowledge outputs adhere to the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) and CARE (Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, Ethics) principles. The aim of this evaluation is to map the compliance of assessments with the DKMP through time and to identify areas for improvement. These findings will help to improve the compliance of future assessments.

Objectives

- To assess the degree of compliance of SUA, VA and IAS with the IPBES DKMP.
- To identify strengths of these assessments which can be used as areas for improvement in the conduct of the ongoing and future assessments.
- To provide actionable recommendations to improve the compliance of future assessments with the DKMP.
- To demonstrate the increasing compliance of IPBES assessments with the DKMP and to promote transparency, accessibility and ethical standards.

Assessment Overview

The three IPBES assessments evaluated in this report are:

1. Sustainable Use Assessment (SUA)
2. Values Assessment (VA)
3. Invasive Alien Species Assessment (IAS)

Each assessment was reviewed against specific criteria set out in the DKMP to determine its level of compliance.

Key Messages

- Compliance with the DKMP has improved significantly, increasing from around 70% in 2022 to 90% in 2023.
- The experience and lessons learned from these assessments will inform future assessments and the DKMP revision process.
- A new maturity model is being considered to prioritise key compliance criteria and provide a more nuanced scoring system.

Detailed Conformity Assessment Results

Sustainable Use Assessment (SUA)

- Overall Score: 69.2%
- Key Issues Identified:
 - Incomplete author lists and missing identifiers in bibliographic references. (Some references lack complete metadata.)
 - Discrepancies in data attribution and documentation.
- Strengths:
 - Improved delivery and accuracy of figures and tables.
 - Effective collaboration between the Technical Support Units (TSUs) to resolve ambiguities.
 - Enhanced efforts in ensuring data provenance and proper metadata tagging.

Values Assessment (VA)

- Overall Score: 72.4%
- Key Issues Identified:
 - Incomplete and inaccurate author lists.
 - Missing identifiers in a significant number of bibliographic references.
 - Variability in data quality and consistency across different chapters and chapter sections.
- Strengths:
 - Improved delivery of data-driven and spatial figures
 - Enhanced clarity and completeness of tables.
 - Better integration of diverse data sources and comprehensive metadata documentation.

Invasive Alien Species Assessment (IAS)

- Overall Score: 93.2%
- Key Issues Identified:
 - Some tables used country names instead of ISO codes.
 - 75 references in the Zotero library missing identifiers.
 - Occasional inconsistencies in data format and standardization.
- Strengths:
 - High compliance in most areas, reflecting rigorous adherence to the DKMP.
 - Excellent collaboration between TSUs and comprehensive data management practices.
 - Strong emphasis on ensuring data accuracy and proper citation management.

In-Depth Summary

Citations and bibliographic references

- Problems with missing identifiers were a common challenge across all assessments, affecting the completeness and reliability of bibliographic data.
- The need for a standardised process for managing citations and references is evident, with suggestions to implement a maturity model to prioritise compliance criteria from essential to useful.
- Specific problems included missing Digital Object Identifier (DOI) numbers, incomplete author lists and inconsistencies in citation formats.

Figures and tables

- The delivery and accuracy of figures and tables has improved significantly, reflecting better compliance with the DKMP.
- Appropriate usage rights and disclaimers have been consistently included to ensure legal and ethical compliance.
- Recommendations include allowing the use of full country names for readability in certain contexts, alongside ISO codes.
- Improve the visual presentation of data to ensure that figures are clear, accurately labelled and properly sourced.

ILK uptake

- Full compliance with free, prior and informed consent was achieved in all assessments involving data from indigenous peoples and local communities.
- Documentation and adherence to the terms of consent were rigorously maintained, demonstrating a strong commitment to ethical standards.
- Ensure that data collected respects the cultural sensitivities and intellectual property rights of indigenous communities.

Disclaimers

- All assessments included the necessary disclaimers, making it clear that no legal opinion was being given on the status of the areas mapped.

Cooperation and coordination

- Effective cooperation between different TSUs, including the Data TSU, was highlighted as a critical factor in achieving high levels of compliance.
- Coordination efforts between the assessment TSUs and the Data TSU led to the resolution of ambiguities, clarification of policies and improved overall data quality.
- Continuous feedback loops and regular communication channels between TSUs facilitated smoother data management processes.

Discussion and Recommendations

- Clear guidelines for bibliography management: Providing clear, step-by-step guidelines for exporting and uploading bibliographies would reduce ambiguity and improve compliance.
- Early delivery of author lists: Ensuring that author lists are provided early in the process would reduce inconsistencies and improve the accuracy of bibliographic references. Author lists should be verified before delivery of each draft to keep them up to date.
- Close collaboration between TSUs: Continued close collaboration between Technical Support Units (TSUs) for the assessments and the Data TSU, and in cases involving

(the handling of) ILK, the ILK TSU is essential to resolve ambiguities and improve compliance.

- Training and capacity building: Regular training and capacity building workshops for all participants (assessment TSUs and the authors) to ensure familiarity with the DKMP guidelines and best practices.
- Regular updates and revisions: Ongoing review and updating of the technical guidelines to incorporate feedback, address emerging challenges and reflect technological advances.

Final remark

The conformity assessment shows a satisfactory level of DKMP compliance across the three IPBES assessments evaluated, indicating significant progress towards the goal of full implementation of the FAIR and CARE principles by 2030. The lessons learned from this assessment will guide revisions to the DKMP and the Delivery Protocol to ensure that future assessments achieve higher levels of compliance and quality.

Appendices

1. Conformity report of IPBES Invasive Alien Species assessment with the data and knowledge management policy; <https://doi/10.5281/zenodo.11613449>
2. Conformity report of IPBES Values and Sustainable Use assessments with the data and knowledge management policy; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7738821>